

Synthesis of heterocycles containing pyrimidine-acridine rings by microwave irradiation, antimicrobial study and its comparison with classical heating

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Abstract : New series of linked heterocycles containing acridine and pyrimidines were prepared in high yield from condensation of *N*-acridin-9-yl-3-oxo-butylamide with urea or thiourea or guanidine by microwave irradiation and by conventional heating for comparative study purpose. The representative compounds characterized on the basis of IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral beside elemental analysis. Microwave assisted synthesized compounds evaluated for their antimicrobial screening against selected microorganisms and some of them found to possess equipotent activity when compared with standard drug.

Keywords : MW reactions, pyrimidines, aminoacridine, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

The search of new potent antimicrobial agent with low impact on environment is gaining importance, not only for medicinal chemistry but in the pharmaceutical production. Microwave technique rapidly developing area provides a number of advantages over the standard heating technique¹. High density microwave irradiation technology has emerged as a reliable and useful methodology for accelerating time consuming reactions². Pyrimidine derivatives have played unique role in the field of medicinal chemistry³ because of known to display antitumor⁴, anticancer⁵, insecticidal⁶ activities. Some pyrimidine derivatives such as 3-azido-3-deoxythymidine⁷ recently developed as an antiviral agent against HIV. On the other hand acridine found to possess wide range of bioactivity profile. Amino derivative of acridine is exhibits efficient antitumor agents⁸. Because of these biological and chemotherapeutic properties of acridine and pyrimidine, attempts have been made to synthesize some new heterocycles containing acridine and pyrimidine moieties together with hope of enhanced microbial activity under different conditions i.e. microwave irradiation and conventional heating for comparative study.

Experimental

All MW irradiation experiments were carried out in the commercially available microwave oven with con-

tinuous irradiation with power of 800 W. All the material used AR grade, starting material obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and solvents were evaporated at 40 °C. TLC is used to monitor the reactions. Melting points were determined on a digital melting point apparatus (Veego-DMP) and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 MHz spectrophotometer in CDCl₃. Chemical shifts are given in ppm and reference to TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were measurements on a Jeol JMC-300 spectrometer at 70 eV by ESI method.

Microwave irradiation method for synthesis of compounds (5a-e) :

Preparation of N-acridin-9-yl-3-oxo-butylamide (3) :

A mixture of 9-aminoacridine (**1**) (0.02 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (**2**) (0.02 mol) in ethanol irradiated under microwave condition for 2 min, afforded *N*-acridin-9-yl-3-oxo-butylamide. Recrystallized the crude product with (95%) ethanol to get pure yellow product and identified as an *N*-acridin-9-yl-3-oxo-butylamide (**3**).

Preparation of 4-(acridin-9-yl-amino)-6-methyl-5H-pyrimidin-2-one (5a) :

N-Acridine-9-yl-3-oxo-butylamide (**3**) (0.02 mol) and urea (**4**) (0.02 mol) were mixed in ethanol and irradiated by MW for 3 min. Reaction monitored by TLC, and then

further purified by recrystallisation from 95% EtOH in cold condition to yield the entitled product 4-(acridin-9-yl-amino)-6-methyl-5H-pyrimidin-2-one (**5**). This reaction further extended to synthesize (**5b-e**).

Conventional heating method for synthesis of compounds (5a-e) :

Preparation of N-acridin-9-yl-3-oxo-butyramide (3) :

A mixture of 9-aminoacridine (**1**) (0.02 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (**2**) (0.02 mol) in ethanol refluxed in oil bath for 3–4 h, afforded *N*-acridin-9-yl-3-oxo-butyramide. Recrystallized the crude product with (95%) ethanol to get pure yellow product and identified as an *N*-acridin-9-yl-3-oxo-butyramide (**3**).

Preparation of 4-(acridin-9-yl-amino)-6-methyl-5H-pyrimidin-2-one (5a) :

N-Acridin-9-yl-3-oxo-butyramide (**3**) (0.02 mol) and urea (**4**) (0.02 mol) were mixed in ethanol refluxed in waterbath for 2–3 h. Reaction monitored by TLC, and crude product recrystallised from 95% EtOH in cold condition to yield the entitled product 4-(acridin-9-yl-amino)-6-methyl-5H-pyrimidin-2-one (**5**). This reaction further extended to synthesize (**5b-e**).

Spectral data of MW synthesized compounds (5a-e) :

5a; ν_{\max} : 3387, 3022, 1626, 1594, 1215 cm^{-1} ; (CDCl_3 + $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 4.8 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.7 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.1 (1H, br s, NH), 7.5–7.4 (8H, m, Acridin-H); m/z 195 (base peak); **5b**; ν_{\max} : 3387, 3022, 1594, 1215 cm^{-1} ; (CDCl_3 + $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.8 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.41 (1H, br s, NH), 8.9 (8H, m, Acridin-H); m/z 195 (base peak); **5c**; ν_{\max} : 3384, 3022, 1594, 1215 cm^{-1} ; (CDCl_3 + $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.7 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.1 (2H, s, NH), 8.14 (1H, s, NH), 7.5–7.4 (8H, m, Acridin-H); m/z 195 (base peak); **5d**; ν_{\max} : 3387, 3022, 1626, 1594, 1215 cm^{-1} ; (CDCl_3 + $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.7 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.1 (2H, s, NH), 7.1–6.8 (5H, m, Aro-H), 7.5–7.4 (8H, m, Acridin-H); m/z 195 (base peak); **5e**; ν_{\max} : 3387, 3022, 1594, 1215 cm^{-1} ; (CDCl_3 + $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.7 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.1–6.8 (5H, m, Aro-H), 7.5–7.4 (8H, m, Acridin-H); m/z 195 (base peak).

Antimicrobial activity :

All the MW synthesized compounds were screened

for antibacterial activity using the agar well diffusion method¹¹. By using sterile pipette 0.2 mL of the broth culture of the test organism was added to an 18-mL sterile molten diagnostic sensitivity test agar, well mixed up to homogeneity and poured into previously sterilized Petri dishes. The wells (diameter 10 mm) were then filled up with the solution of the compound in DMSO aseptically using Pasteur pipettes. Streptomycin was used as a standard antibacterial agent at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. The plates were allowed to stand for about 1 h and then incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The relative susceptibility of the bacteria to compounds **5a-e** and streptomycin standard is recorded by measuring inhibition zones in mm using antibiotic zone scale.

Table 1. Microwave and conventional synthesis of compounds (**5a-e**)

Entry	Product	m.p. (°C)		Yields (%)	
		MW	Δ	MW	Δ
4	5				
Urea		256	254	78	74
Thiourea		212	209	93	84
Guanidine		200	199	96	78
Phenyl urea		182	180	91	80
Phenyl thiourea		152	148	84	72

Results and discussion

The present comparative study reports the microwave and conventional synthesis of acridine linked pyrimidine derivatives with microbial activity. Microwave procedure offers several advantages over conventional method including operation simplicity, no side reactions, less reaction time and minimum environmental impact makes it

useful process of synthesis. The homogeneity of compounds is checked by TLC. The spectral analysis IR, ^1H NMR^{9,10} and Mass spectra besides elemental analysis found complete agreement with the expected results. All the compounds were found to have an effective response against some selected microorganisms like *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *K. pneumonia*, *P. vulgerius* and *P. aeruginosa*.

Reaction Scheme

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of synthesized compounds (5a-e)

Compounds	Microorganisms with inhibition zone recorded (mm)				
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>P. vulgerius</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
5a	21	21	19	14	13
5b	21	22	14	11	13
5c	19	21	13	11	12
5d	22	21	20	14	13
5e	20	22	13	12	14
Streptomycin	20	22	15	15	14

Conclusion

Microwave assisted synthesis of heterocycles containing acridine and a pyrimidine motif in comparison with the conventional heating is described. Microwave product obtained in excellent yields (75–90%) at short reaction time (5–10 min) over conventional products. The linked heterocyclic compounds due to presence of above mentioned biodynamic moieties exhibited potent activity against selected microorganisms.

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